

Solute-Solvent Interactions in Solutions of Potassium Acetate in Water and Aqueous Methyl Acetate

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Gross solute-solvent interaction in solutions of potassium acetate in water and in aqueous methyl acetate (20% by weight) has been deduced from the values of apparent molar volume determined by precise density measurement, relative viscosity and the B-coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation and from conductance studies at different concentrations and at 25°, 30°, 40° and 50°. It is found that the salt behaves as structure maker in water and in aqueous methyl acetate.

SOLUTE-solvent interaction studies have been a subject of active interest among physical chemists¹⁻⁶ and mostly the inferences regarding these interactions are drawn from conductance⁷, molar volume data⁸ and viscosity data^{9,10} together. Literature is full of such studies in pure solvents. Studies in mixed solvents are of considerable interest because peculiar results are obtained¹¹ in most of the solvent systems. The present study is carried out in connection with the work on physico-chemical studies of systems involving acetates and the main object of the paper has been to arrive at the nature of solute-solvent interaction from the molar volume, viscous flow and conductance properties of potassium acetate in water and aqueous methyl acetate (when one of the constituents of the solute and solvent has some common features).

Experimental

Potassium acetate was used after crystallisation from anhydrous acetic acid and pumped dry under vacuum for 30 hours at 100°. Methyl acetate was purified by treating with potassium carbonate and later distilled after keeping for an overnight over P₂O₅. The conductivity, density and viscosity of methyl acetate at 30° used were 3.8 × 10⁻⁶ ohm⁻¹cm⁻¹, 0.92065 g.ml⁻¹ and 0.00351 poise respectively and these values agree with literature values^{12,13}. The water conductivity of order 10⁻⁶ ohm⁻¹cm⁻¹ was used for making 20% (by weight) aqueous methyl acetate. The density¹⁴, viscosity measurements⁹ and conductance¹⁵ measurements were carried out by the method described earlier. All measurements except of viscosity were made in the water bath placed in an air thermostat with temperature fluctuations always below 0.02°. In case of viscosity, measurements were carried out in air thermostat having temperature fluctuations of the order ±0.05°. The viscosity of the water used for calculation were 0.8937 cp, 0.8007 cp, 0.656 cp and 0.5494 cp at 25°, 30°, 40° and 50° respectively. The densities were taken as given in the literature¹².

Results and Discussion

The density of the various solutions, d , can be represented by the Root's equation¹⁶:

$$d = d_0 + AC - BC^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

where d_0 is the density of the solvent, C is the concentration, and A and B are the constants of the Root's equation. On plotting $d-d_0/C$ versus \sqrt{C} a straight line should be obtained and we get straight line in each case as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Values of A and B

Plot of $d-d_0/C$ vs \sqrt{C} for potassium acetate in water at different temperatures

Fig. 1

Plot of $d-d_0/c$ vs \sqrt{C} for potassium acetate in aqueous methyl acetate (20%) at different temperatures

Fig. 2

evaluated from the intercept and slope of the plots are given with the ligands of the graph 1 and 2.

The apparent molar volume, $\phi_v^{\bar{v}}$, is calculated from the density data by the equation¹⁷ :

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{m d d_0} + \frac{M_2}{d} \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_v represents the molar volume of the electrolyte, d the density of the solution, d_0 the density of the solvent, m is the molality of the solutions and M_2 the molecular weight of the electrolyte.

The apparent molar volume has been found to vary with concentration according to Masson's equation¹⁸ and the data can be represented by the relation :

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^{\circ} + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_v° is the limiting apparent molar volume, and S_v is the experimental slope. Here ϕ_v° is a measure of solute-solvent interaction and S_v is a measure of ion-ion interaction. The limiting apparent molar volume, ϕ_v° , for different systems calculated from the linear graph of ϕ_v versus \sqrt{C} as shown in Figs. 3 and 4 are given in Table 1.

The greater magnitude of ϕ_v° in case of water suggests that the solute-solvent interaction is greater in case of water. Further, Table 1 shows that it increases with increase of temperature in water and aqueous methyl acetate. The increase in the ϕ_v° of potassium

Plot of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} for potassium acetate in water at different temperatures

Fig. 3

Plot of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} for potassium acetate in aqueous methyl acetate (20%) at different temperatures

Fig. 4

acetate in water and in aqueous methyl acetate with increasing temperature may be attributed to the increase

TABLE 1—VALUE OF ϕ_v^0 FOR DIFFERENT SYSTEMS.

System	Temperature (°C)	ϕ_v^0 (ml.mol ⁻¹)
Potassium acetate in water	25	42.80
	30	46.10
	40	51.00
	50	54.01
Potassium acetate in aqueous methyl acetate (20%)	25	38.00
	30	38.50
	40	38.80
	50	46.50

in the solute-solvent interactions. The temperature coefficient ($\partial\phi_v^0/\partial t$) increases with increase of temperature¹⁹ in both the solvents. Using Hepler's reasoning of long-range interactions, we find that potassium acetate behaves as a structure maker because ($\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial t^2$) is positive, and the accommodation of the solute in the void space left in the packing of the large associated solvent molecules and the greater solvation of inorganic ions with methyl acetate is not unexpected.

The data on viscosity was analysed with the help of the Jones-Dole²⁰ equation :

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (4)$$

where η is the viscosity of the solution, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, C is the molar concentration and A and B are constants characteristic of the solute electrolyte. A coefficient represents the contribution from interionic electrostatic force²¹. The B coefficient is said to be a measure of the effective hydrodynamic volume of the solvated ions²² and to denote the order or disorder introduced by the ions into the solvent structure. The values of A and B of equation (4) are determined from the intercept and slope of the straight line plots of $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Values of A and B parameters at different temperatures are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—JONES-DOLE PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR DIFFERENT SYSTEMS.

System	Temperature (°C)	A	B
Potassium acetate in water	25	0.008	0.237
	30	0.010	0.234
	40	0.010	0.226
	50	0.010	0.214
Potassium acetate in 20% methyl acetate	25	-0.009	0.370
	30	-0.006	0.357
	40	-0.005	0.333
	50	-0.004	0.280

Test of Jones-Dole equation for potassium acetate in water at different temperatures

Fig. 5

Test of Jones-Dole equation for potassium acetate in aqueous methyl acetate (20%) at different temperatures

Fig. 6

In the Jones-Dole equation, A is a calculable parameter and is similar for all 1:1 electrolytes. The A-parameter was found to be slightly higher than the observed value of 0.0066 for lithium acetate in water by Laurence and Wolfenden²³ and Cox and Wolfenden²⁴ obtained +0.238 as the value of the B-coefficient which is in good agreement with the value obtained in the present investigation. The negative temperature coefficient of B-parameter dB/dT suggests that the salt behaves like a structure maker²⁵ in case of water.

In case of solutions of aqueous methyl acetate negative values of A have been obtained and such negative values have been obtained in most of the cases involving mixed solvents^{26,27}. The negative temperature coefficient of B, dB/dT suggests that the salt behaves as a structure maker in the aqueous methyl acetate. The large B-coefficient in aqueous methyl acetate (20%) shows that a large ion behaves as more obstacle (than in water) in a way similar to that of a colloidal particle.

The limiting equivalent conductance, Λ_0 , at different temperatures is evaluated from Onsager's plots²⁸, and with the help of Owen's method²⁹. This is based on the conductance equation :

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 - SC^{\frac{1}{2}} + AC \log C + BC \quad (5)$$

where S is the limiting Onsager slope, C is the concentration, A and B are constants.

The limiting equivalent conductance, Λ_0 , along with the Walden product, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$, is given in the Table 3.

TABLE 3—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE, Λ_0 , WALDEN PRODUCT, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$, FOR POTASSIUM ACETATE

Temperature (°C)	Λ_0 (Onsager) (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	Λ_0 (Owen) (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$
Water			
25	116.50	114.75	1.022
30	140.50	137.50	1.097
40	172.50	169.30	1.111
50	215.00	211.00	1.159
20% Aqueous Methyl Acetate			
25	104.00	102.40	1.207
30	138.00	134.50	1.307
40	164.00	161.50	1.340
50	202.00	196.80	1.354

The structural effect on the conductance of ions in solutions can be derived by a comparison of the Walden product ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) at different temperatures²⁵. The positive

temperature coefficient of the Walden product in both the systems suggests that salt behaves like a structure maker. These conclusions are in agreement with those derived from viscosity measurements.

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